

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17278299

Effect of Budgetary Balances on Industrial Production in Nigeria 1987-2022

¹Umeifekwem Chinyere Marietta; ²Prof Umeora Chinweobo & ³Dr Lawrence Uchenna Okoye

¹Department of Commerce Cooperative,
School of Business Education,
Federal College of Education (Technical Umunze), Nigeria
Email; chinvereumeifekwem2011@gmail.com

^{2,3}Department of Banking and Finance
Faculty of Management Sciences
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of budgetary balances on industrial production in Nigeria, classifying budgetary balances into Budget deficit Investment as percentage of GDP, Inflation rate, Interest rate, Exchange rate and Oil revenue were developed based on Keynesian fiscal policy theory. An ex-post facto research design was adopted, and data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin and Annual Reports and accounts as well as the World Bank's Development Indicators, covering a 36-year period from 1987 to 2022. The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model, which allows for the combination of time series at both levels I(0) and first differences I(1), was employed to analyze the impact of these budgetary balances on industrial production. The findings revealed that Budgetary balances had a significant long-run impact of 3.09% and a 92% short-run effect on industrial production. The study concluded that budgetary balances were not key drivers of industrial production in Nigeria. To foster industrial growth, the Nigerian government should prioritize fiscal discipline by managing budgetary balances, implementing tax reforms that support short-term growth, and optimizing public expenditure and investment for immediate industrial stimulation while ensuring long-term sustainability. Additionally, maintaining public debt at sustainable levels is crucial to prevent long-term economic burdens, ensuring short-term fiscal gains do not undermine future industrial development. The study contributed to knowledge by developing distinct models for analyzing the effects of budgetary balances on industrial production.

Keywords: Budgetary Balances, Industrial Production, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

A balanced budget occurs when revenues are equal to or greater than total expenses (Mohammed & Sule, 2020). A budget can be considered balanced after a full year of revenues and expenses have been incurred and recorded. Proponents of a balanced budget argue that budget deficits burden future generations with debt. A balanced budget is a budget in which revenues are equal to expenditures. Thus, neither a budget deficit nor a budget surplus exists. Specifically, it is a budget that has no budget deficit, but could possibly have a budget surplus (Onuah & Bela-Gbogbo, 2023).

Fiscal policy is the strategy through which the government influences taxation and other sources of funds in order to finance government expenses and activities for the purposes of creating a stable economy and

welfare of the citizenry. Fiscal policy tools listed by Economicsdiscussion.net (Retrieved, 13th November, 2023) include government expenditure, taxation, deficit financing through budgetary balances, public works and public debt management. They are used to meet certain macroeconomic targets among which are management of unemployment, price stability, economic growth and development.

Industrial policy can be an important and powerful instrument for stimulating rapid economic growth and development. From the inception of the Nigeria's independence, various governments have been trying a range of approaches centered on meeting the needs of the citizenry. The outcome of these policies have been a huge failure and unpredictably, favoring "rent seeking" (Yusuf & Mohd, 2023). For instance, Import Substitution Policy (1962 to 1968), later replaced with the indigenization policy known as the Nigerian Enterprises Promotion Decree (1970 to 1974), Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) of the mid 1986 and Export Expansion Grant (EEG) (suspended in 2014 and reintroduced in 2017), and the Nigeria Industrial Revolution Plan (2014) all are well designed but fail at implementation (see Effiong, 2022; Anudu, 2020). More so, the recent array of government policies of the past administration from 2015 to 2018, like the National Irrigation and Drainage Policy and Strategy, National Policy on the Environment, and Power Sector Recovery Program, (see Appendix 9) have equally not fared satisfactorily well.

For over a decade in Nigeria, industrial growth has been dwindling. The trends in Figure 1 shows that industrial production index has remained on the negatives for many periods from 2007. Industrial Production in Nigeria averaged 0.51 percent from 2007 until 2023, reaching an all time high of 27.60 percent in the first quarter of 2011 and a record low of -16.80 percent in the fourth quarter of 2016. Austere economic trends lasted till late 2022 with a -2.30% index of industrial production but the first quarter of 2023 showed a tremendous increase of 15.20 percent in Nigeria. This trends explains the level of economic uncertainty occasioned by the industrial growth prospects in Nigeria.

Figure 1: Trends in industrial production in Nigeria from 2007 to 2022

Source: Trading Economics; Nigeria Industrial Production, retrieved from

<https://tradingeconomics.com/nigeria/industrial-production>

Fiscal policy issues in Nigeria led to long period of deficit, and public debts with government policies to divest many public investments in electricity, air ports, banking, and even communications. The oil revenue which has remained the major source of federal government revenue from the 70s has remained the major determinant of the fiscal policy dynamics in Nigeria. Oil revenue has remained persistently unstable since 1974 till date causing economic uncertainty to Nigerian industrial sector, hence fiscal

policy dynamics in Nigeria has changed drastically towards diversifying revenue base and increased taxation. The attendant effects on the industrial sector has not been succinctly address in Nigerian context. The Gross Domestic Product growth rate, capacity utilization and Index of Industrial production as indicators of growth has remained low and dwindling over the past decades. As industrial growth have remained a perennial economic challenge to successive governments in Nigeria. As countries with low index of industrial production as Nigeria has high tendency to remain in unemployment and less comparative advantage of nations, a review of the effect of fiscal policy dynamics in Nigeria on the improving industrial growth paradigm is pertinent. Hence, the need to investigate the effect of Budgetary Balances on Industrial Production in Nigeria

Statement of the Problem

The industrial sector in Nigeria, despite its huge potential to drive economic diversification and sustainable development, has faced significant challenges in achieving desired objective. Fiscal policies, particularly government taxation, public spending, and debt management strategies, play a critical role in shaping the industrial landscape. However, the effectiveness of these fiscal policies in stimulating industrial sector growth remains unclear. There is limited empirical evidence on how fiscal policy dynamics, such as government expenditure allocations, tax incentives, and deficit financing, have either promoted or hindered industrial growth in Nigeria. Understanding the intricate relationship between fiscal policies and industrial sector performance is crucial to formulating strategies that can accelerate industrialization and improve economic resilience. The problem, therefore, lies in examining whether the current fiscal policy framework effectively supports industrial growth, and if not, what policy adjustments are necessary to address persistent constraints such as inadequate infrastructure, high production costs, and limited access to capital.

Theoretical postulations have given diverse explanations to impact of fiscal policy dynamics on growth. Extant studies in Nigeria have not clearly supported any of the fiscal policy - growth nexus. For instance, Nwaeke (2023) support fiscal deficit and Eche, Pam, Akeem, and Salawu (2022) disagreed which connote gross divergence in the fiscal deficit - industrial growth nexus. Also, it was found that conflict exists on the effect of taxes on growth. For example Omolade, Omolade and Adebusuyi (2023), Olognela (2022) all saw positive relations between taxation and industrial growth but some others like Oladipo, *et al* (2019) noted that such relationship is either not significant or outright negative. This divergence in findings calls for further empirical investigating of fiscal policy implications on Nigerian industrial growth. This study becomes pertinent in present dispensation that Nigeria is seeking to attract private investment to develop the industry and secure a sustainable economy for the nation. This study therefore aims to investigate the effect of Budgetary Balances on Industrial Production in Nigeria 1987-2022

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Budgetary Balances

Omolehinwa (1989) as cited in Onaolapo and Olaoye (2013), defined a budget as a plan of dominant individuals in an organization expressed in monetary terms and subject to the constraints imposed by the participants and the environments, indicating how the available resources may be utilized, to achieve whatever the dominant individuals agreed to be the organisation's priorities. Pandey (2021) defines a budget as a short term financial plan. It is an action plan to guide managers in achieving the objectives of the firm. Lucey (2003) in his definition of budget sees it as a quantitative presentation of a plan of action prepared for the business as a whole for departments, for functions such as sales and production or for financial resource items such as cash, capital expenditure, manpower purchase, etc.

Generally, the process of preparing budgets is a means of translating the overall objectives of the organization into detailed, feasible plans of action, which implies it is beyond a financial tool (Morgan, 1997 as cited in Igbekoyi, 2015). Thus, a budget can be used to take decisions on key resources, especially performance resource are assigned to priorities and results. On this premise, Morgan emphasized that budgets should be used as a tool for planning and control. However the concept of control details the decisions fashioned from available relevant information that brings about plans and

actions that improve the utilization of the productive assets and services available to organizations management (Hudson & Andrew, 1996 cited in Onaolapo & Olaoye, 2013). Effective control is the basic standards on which actual performance can be compared.

From these definitions of budgets, we distinguish three key components. Firstly, we recognize the planning aspect of the budget. The plan is regarded as the statement of intent or goal of the organization. The second aspect is measurability. This makes it possible to measure the plan. The third component is time. It gives the possibility to say if the plan is achieved.

On a broader basis, the budget is not only an instrument of economic and social policy but also a planning tool, an instrument for coordination, and an instrument for communication. A good budget, therefore, requires comprehensiveness, a meaningful presentation of the state of budgetary balance and an appropriate grouping of expenditure items (Anyanwu, 1997 cited in Asaju, Adagba & Kajang, 2014).

Budgetary balance is derived from the difference between a budgeted amount and the actual amount spent. In most suitable parlance, it is the difference between what the government spends and what the government collects over a period of time, usually for one year (Testic, Ilic & Delic, 2014). When the government spends more than it collects, a budget deficit exists. Put more accurately, budget deficit arises when the revenue and past accumulation of past savings become inadequate to finance the expenditure gap still left on the current and capital accounts (Chukwu, Otiwu & Okere, 2020). However, when the government collects more than it spends, a budget surplus exists. The concept of budget deficit occurs when the government is in the practice of raising government expenditures beyond revenue sources in order to stimulate a country's economy, (Oniore, & Adamu, 2021), whereas surplus is the deliberate effort to spend below the budget.

Both surplus and deficit budgets are deliberate efforts of the government. When the government runs a budget deficit, it is said to be engaging in fiscal stimulus, spurring economic activity, and when the government runs a budget surplus, it is said to be engaging in a fiscal contraction, slowing economic activity. Fiscal deficit, therefore, can be seen as a situation where government plans to spend more in a year than the revenue it expects to collect. In this case, the government experiences a budget deficit equal to the amount by which the expenditure exceeds the revenue. In other words, budget deficit is the amount of that extra expenditure the government wants to undertake above the expected revenue (Eche, *et al*, 2022).

In most developing countries like Nigeria, deficit financing is the most predominant aspect of public sector budgeting. Government budget deficit in any given economy can be financed by using monetary finance and debt finance. Monetary financing of a budget deficit has to do with printing (creation of money) of currency by the monetary authority, the revenue accruing from which is called "seigniorage" (Nzotta, 2004; Chukwu, Otiwu & Okere, 2020). In this situation, the government offers in the market a stock of money that exceeds the amount objectively justified to be in circulation in the economy. The term deficit financing is used to denote the direct addition to gross national expenditure through budget deficits whether the deficits are on the revenue or capital account. The persistent government budget deficits and government debt have become major concern in both developed and developing countries (Awe & Shina, 2012).

Industrialization and Industrial Growth

Industrialization is the process of turning an economy based on extraction into an economy based on production. A nation's economic wellbeing is directly linked to its degree of industrialization and material resourcefulness, on the basis of which nations are divided into emerging, developing and developed countries (Omankhanlen, Chimezie & Okoye, 2021). Williams opined that the replacement of hand tools by machine and power tools is the sine qua non of an industrialized society, but that industrialization also involves vast economic and changes - a tendency toward urbanization, a growing body of earners, increased technical and advanced education (Bubou, Ejim-Eze, Ogungbemi & Okgriwe, 2013).

Industrialization includes policy policies in the planning and establishment of industries for job creation, poverty alleviation, income equality, etc., which in turn leads to national production growth. Industrial growth and development could be considered the heartbeat of any successful economy. The emphasis on industrial aspects of public finances in modern economic development systems stems from the fact that

the industrial sector is the long-term medium for sustained growth due to the fact that the industrial sector provides the requisite leverage for competitive participation in foreign trade, expansion of domestic capacity and creation of good job opportunities (Omankhanlen, *et al* 2021).

Amughoro (2021) posit that industrial growth is an offshoot of economic growth. According to him, for industrial growth to ensue, there must be sufficient availability of factors of production of the right quality and sufficient demand in the market. First, there must be sufficient labour skill in the techniques and technologies of production. The producer must therefore be skilled and educated, or at least in a position where they are capable of being trained and willing to learn new skills. Second, there must be sufficient capital. The purchase of new capital equipment requires finance which must be available from retained profits of firms or well organized capital market (or in the case government investment from taxation. Third, land must be available and must be a suitable infrastructure (roads, railways communication networks etc.) to support commercial activity. Fourth, the government policy should be to achieve economic growth because if there is an alternative economic objective (e.g. restoring a balance of payment equilibrium) government policy might suppress growth. Fifth, international trade should be encouraged as a means of growth; this is because international trade opens up new markets for exporters and same for importers. Lastly, technical progress is very important source of faster economic growth. Technical progress means that the same amounts of the factor of production can produce higher output. The industrial production the western world has was a period of concentrated technological developments leading to an understanding in the rate leading to an outstanding increase in the rate of their growth.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is hinged on views of fiscal policy effects on an economy which are Neoclassical, Keynesian and Ricardian theories. The Neoclassical theorists posit that public investment (government spending) and the attendant deficit financing will always crowd-out private investment and reduce growth. The Keynesians, on the contrary, posit that government expenditure will crowd-in private sector investment with the view to boost growth while the third group which propounded the Ricardian equivalence posit that government spending has no effect on private investment vis-a-vis growth. The ideologies of these theories formed the theoretical framework of this study. These theories are relevant to the present study because the resultant effect of fiscal policy dynamics is dependent on the effectiveness of the policy. Thus, fiscal policy effects may take any of the three forms: positive, negative or no effect as proposed by the Keynesian, Neoclassical and Ricardian proponents respectively.

Empirical Studies

Budgetary balances can result to deficit or surplus budgets. The work of Nwaeke (2023) that investigated the impact of budget deficit and foreign direct investment on Nigerian economy from the period 1990 to 2022. Exchange rate, foreign direct investment, government deficit financing, inflation rate and real gross domestic product were used as measures and dimension respectively. Results from Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimates revealed that in the long run, exchange rate (EXR), foreign direct investment (FDI), government deficit financing (GDF) have positive and significant impact on real gross domestic product while inflation rate (INFR) has negative impact on real gross domestic product in the Nigerian economy. The study recommends amongst others that fiscal deficit should be channeled to productive investment such as roads construction, provision of electricity, improved health system to mention but three that would serve as incentives to productivity through the attraction of foreign direct investments.

Eche *et al* (2022) examined the impact of fiscal deficit on Nigeria economic growth between 1981 to 2020 through autoregressive distributed lag approach (ARDL). The study used gross domestic product (GDP) as the dependent variable. Government deficit financing (GDF), interest rate (INT) exchange rate (EXR) and inflation rate (INF) as the independent variables. A cointegration test revealed the presence of long run relationship. The result of the long-run ARDL cointegration revealed (GDF) exert negative impact on (GDP). This shows that a 1% rise in (GDF) depresses (GDP) by 18.6%. more so, INT and EXR also exhibited inverse relationship with (GDP). Only INF was found to exert positive impact on (GDP).

This study thus posit that fiscal deficit financing exerts negative impact on growth, and hence recommended that government borrowing should be capital and infrastructural investment focused, and received in form of projects and not liquid cash.

Ushie and Ndu (2022) aimed to examined the real impact of budget deficit financing on the economic development of Nigeria, among which is estimating budget and its deficit financed components from the period 2011-2020 on inflation rate and economic growth. The result from Ordinary Least Square revealed that budget deficit financing has significant relationship with inflation rate. The study thus recommended the adoption of viable alternative fiscal economic tools to source for funds to finance government projects and programs, rather than borrowing locally or externally to finance budget deficit and piling up debts to the detriment of the citizens.

Nwankpa (2022) joined numerous researchers to infer believe that public sector deficit financing should have implications on economic growth of a nation; and then developed a model to examine the influence of credit to government, Non-bank public credit, ways and means, and external deficit financing on economic growth of Nigeria within the period covering 2003 to 2018. With the aid a regression analysis using log-linear of real GDP as the dependent variable, the study found that budget financing through bank credit and non-bank public are positively proportional to the growth rate of Nigerian economy. It further showed that financing through ways and means is inversely related to real GDP growth. The result for external financing exhibited inverse relationship with the growth rate of Nigerian economy but the coefficient of EXDF was not statistically significant. It then recommended that government should weigh the risks associated with external borrowing as well as consider the medium and long-term repercussions of a possible default on debt servicing.

Onwuka (2022) equally employed the disaggregated Vector Autoregression (VAR) approach to investigate the impact of deficit financing on economic growth with inflation as an interaction variable. The results showed that overall deficit financing had a positive and significant impact on economic growth when financed through external sources but had a deleterious effect when financed through domestic sources. It thus posit that the result followed a theoretically assumption of the crowding-out effect of the private sector when deficit financing is funded through the domestic loan market.

Nwikina, *et al* (2021), examine the effectiveness of deficit financing as a veritable instrument to enhance economic development in Nigeria from 1986 to 2019. Economic development was proxied by human development index, while deficit financing by budget deficit and government expenditure. They adopted the ARDL model and granger causality techniques in their analysis and the result shows that budget deficit and government expenditure exert positive but marginal influence on economic development in Nigeria. Furthermore, a unidirectional causality was discovered, indicating that deficit financing through government expenditure promotes economic development in Nigeria. However, the outcome of the research in tandem with the Keynesian theory, deficit financing value in Nigeria is not substantive enough to drive the desired development of the economy.

Oniore and Adamu (2021) employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) to examine the impact of budget deficit finance on Nigerian economy growth. The study built deficit budget, interest and exchange rate as the independent variables regressed on GDP covering 1981 to 2019. The co-integration test revealed the co-integration of the variables and that the Error Correction Model is signed negatively and highly significant statistically at one percent, as anticipated. The estimated Error correction model showed that budget deficit and exchange rate are the key drivers of economic growth in the short-run. Similarly, only budget deficit appears to spur economic growth in the long-run. As further findings revealed that budget deficit financing is an important source of economic growth to the country, it was recommended that the Federal Government should checkmate the level of deficits spending and boost the country's productive capacity, facilitate a favourable investment climate through appropriate monetary policy transmission channels like interest rate spread.

Chigbo (2021) employed Johansen co-integration analysis and Error Correction Model (ECM) to examine the relationship between economic growth in Nigeria and Public external debt, total federal collection revenue, and interest rate. The public deficit financing was determined based on the study by the variables of Government expenditure, real GDP, exchange rate. The best model of ECM to determine the impact of

fiscal deficit in Nigeria is the interaction with economic growth performance measures in Nigeria. The findings confirm that one standard deviation of shocks of fiscal deficit has a significant influence on economic growth, hence confirming the long-run relationship. The search recommended that Government should set its priority rights, be more committed to the budget implementation, and pay more attention to capital expenditure geared towards economic growth.

Adebowale (2021) examined the asymmetry in the nexus between budget deficit and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018 using a nonlinear ARDL model. The study modeled Oil Revenue, Inflation rate, Trade Openness, Exchange rate and Budget Deficit as fiscal policy dynamic against economic growth proxied by Real Gross Domestic Product. The findings showed found presence of asymmetries in the nexus between the variables in the model in the short and long run; and further posit that budget deficit affect economic growth both in the short and long run negatively. It thus opined the need for the government to ensure proper monitoring of the budget implementation as well as ensuring fiscal discipline among all tiers of government and parastatal in the country.

Kryeziu and Hoxha (2021) used a panel data model to examine the impact of deficits on economic development in Eurozone countries from 1995 to 2015, with a total of 257 observations. The study used the least squares regression method using a multivariate linear regression model. The study's findings revealed that the variable deficit to GDP ratio is statistically significant with a positive sign, and that its expansion has a favorable impact on economic growth. In terms of policy recommendations, it is suggested that the level of high and long-term deficits be controlled for the countries studied because this situation, with a persistently high fiscal deficit, could harm economic growth and create imbalances in other macroeconomic variables, especially now, given the deteriorating situation as a result of the Covid-19 Pandemic. However, study findings are subject to the usual caveats about cross-country regression studies. This is a major limitation of the study.

Using the ARDL bounds test, Yusuf and Abolaji (2021) looked at the impact of Nigeria's budget deficit on growth. The findings found that gross domestic savings, interest rates, budget deficits are all associated substantially with long-term economic growth, but economic growth has only beneficial effects on budget and gross domestic savings in the short term. The study revealed that Nigeria's budget deficit has a significant impact on the economic growth of the country. This means that in Nigeria the Keynesian hypothesis is correct. The study concluded, therefore, that higher gross domestic savings will lead to higher gross domestic investment, leading to greater growth. In order to gain sufficient investment resources, the interest rate is essential to stimulate savings. As a result, the nation's productivity will rise in the long run. However, the study lacks good theoretical foundations as there is justification for control variables used; as econometric methodology adopted can't be relied upon.

Olisaji & Onuora (2021) examined the impact of fiscal policy on the growth of Nigerian economy between 2015 and 2019 using the ordinary regression model. Government Expenditure and Government revenue through Companies Income Tax (CIT) were regressed against dependent variable Economic Growth proxied by GDP growth. The result revealed, that there is a significant and positive relationship between Companies Income Tax and economic growth. On the same note, the study found an insignificant and negative relationship between government expenditure and economic growth (GDP). They recommended that government should formulate and implement workable fiscal policy options that will enhance economic growth.

Jakpa and Osho-Itsueli (2020) also ARDL to investigate the relationship between deficit financing and economy of Nigeria from 1990 to 2019. Deficit financing was proxied by domestic money supply, government fiscal deficit, and inflation rate as control variable in the model. The results showed that all the variables had a significant effect on the economy (GDP) with domestic money supply inducing positive impact while inflation and government fiscal deficit having a negative. The study thus posited that deficit financing has no immediate impact on the economy, but long-term effects. It thus advised that the macroeconomic administrators should be proactive, concise and decisive on the implementation of the midterm expenditure framework (MTEF) as regards to capital projects execution, and define the optimal fiscal intervention measures to foster macroeconomic productivity to avoid misappropriation of public fund.

Gyasi (2020) used the boundaries test (ARDL) methodology to cointegration to investigate the long and short term correlations between macroeconomic variables, fiscal deficit, and economic development in Morocco. The findings revealed that the Moroccan economy's budget deficit has a long-term impact on economic

growth, since the equilibrium adjustment was shown to be relatively swift. According to the report, the Government should boost and monitor tax collections and enhance the indirect tax-to-direct tax ratio. The tax base of the economy should be broadened. While strengthening price stability in the economy, the government should limit its spending. The growth framework used is weak: the independent variables included do not coincide with the conventional persuasion of what basically determines growth.

Yusuff and Abolaji (2020) examined the influence of the budget deficit on the growth of Nigeria economy from 1981 to 2016. The result from ARDL bounds test showed a long run cointegrating relationships and that gross domestic savings, interest rate, and budget deficit had significant relationship with economic growth while in the short run, only budget deficit and gross domestic savings had a positive influence on economic growth. The study posit that budget deficit has a significant impact on economic growth of Nigeria such that the Keynesian theory is true for Nigeria. It thus recommended higher gross domestic savings as a means to manage increasing industrial cum economic growth.

Mohammed and Sule (2020) used time series quarterly data from 2000 to 2019 to investigate the relationship between deficit funding asymmetry and Nigerian economic growth. The analysis is based on Keynesian, monetary neo-liberal theoretical postulations, asymmetry and linkages of importance between deficit funding and the Nigerian economy. The Non-Linear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) approach was used in this investigation. According to the calculated NARDL model, Innovation funding both positive and negative deficits hinder economic growth; yet innovation is financed by a negative deficit has a bigger impact than positive deficit financing innovation. Furthermore, Poor institutions and a lack of savings culture are driving the Nigerian economy, as evidenced by the negative signals of both savings and quality institution coefficients. As a result, the study lends support for fiscal governance by reviewing laws that strengthen existing institutions in accordance with international best practices to guide and monitor the implementation of deficit financing in investment-based projects that can result in higher living standards for citizens. The study suffered from weak growth framework and no robustness checks are offered.

Emefiele, *et al* (2019) examined the effect of deficit budget on the growth of Nigeria Economy, which modeled deficit, inflation and government expenditure on the growth of Nigeria Economy. The findings showed that deficit budget, and inflation had no significant effect on economic growth (GDP); and there is a significant relationship between government expenditure and economic growth (GDP). The study then recommended the beneficial strategy to manage and finance budget deficit is improving the revenue base rather than domestic borrowing.

Osemwengie and Shaibu (2018), investigates the inter-relationships between deficit financing (DF), oil price movement and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2014. The study employed granger causality test and the 2SLS estimation techniques in a semi-log form after first considering the status of identification of the equations in the system. Both rank and order conditions of identification showed that the model was identified. The findings revealed the existence of a strong relationship between real GDP and oil price movement while deficit financing (DF) proved to be weak determinant of real GDP. In the model of oil price movement, only real GDP proved to be significant at 5 per cent while DF managed to explain oil price movement at 10 per cent level. Both real GDP and oil price movement proved to be significant determinants of DF. Uni-directional relationship exists between real GDP and DF; oil price movement and DF while a bi-directional relationship exists between real GDP and oil price movement.

Gaps in Literature

The reviewed extant studies did not take into cognizance the implication of control variables in the results for fiscal policies in Nigeria. For instance, in Nigerian context, crude oil is one sole factor that influences all fiscal policy dynamics from revenue generation, to government expenditure and public debt issues. The present study will consider this and develop models that will factor in oil revenue is moderator of fiscal policy in Nigeria.

Among the reviewed literature, no extant study has specifically examined the effect of budget deficit on industrial sector output in Nigeria. Most of the studies have related fiscal policy to the whole economy using the GDP.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used *ex-post facto* research design. The *ex-post facto* design is a suitable method since the data relating to the variables of the study were obtained as already existing in reputable databases and the researcher does not have the capacity to change their state or direction in the course of the exercise (Onwumere, 2009; Kerlinger, 1973). The data were analyzed with econometric techniques involving Econometric techniques, including Augmented Dicker Fuller tests for unit roots, The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) approach which is capable of handling both stationary at level I(0) and first difference I(1). jio

Model Specifications

Budget-Industrial Growth Model

The model of the budget-industrial growth nexus is hinged on the Keynesian proportion of crowding in hypothesis. The model is modified from those of Osemwengie & Shaibu (2018) and Eche, *et al* (2022). The work of Osemwengie & Shaibu (2018) employed deficit budget and oil price movement as independent variables of budgetary balance. The model captured the effect of oil revenue in an oil rich nation as Nigeria. In addition, Eche, *et al* (2022) factored in interest rate, exchange rate and inflation rate in to the model with deficit budget as the main variable. Budgetary balance can be surplus or deficit, any of which is determined by economic situation (stable of unstable). The study incorporate Budget Balance (+/-) as main variable of the study and controlled it for measures of economic stability as inflation rate, interest rate and exchange rate. In line with the theoretical review, all the variables were modeled into the current study, as follows

$$IIP = f(BD, INFL, INT, EXR, OR)$$

Where:

IIP= Index of Industrial Production

BD = Budget deficit Investment as percentage of GDP

INFL = Inflation rate

INT = Interest rate

EXR = Exchange rate

OR = Oil revenue

The Apriori expectation following the Keynesian view: BD has positive effect while INT has negative effect. INFL and EXR can be positive or negative.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Stationarity Test of the Variables

Time series data are expected to respond to stochastic trends that can distort normal trends and affect the reliability of regression analyses. The variables were therefore subjected to to Augmented Dicker Fuller (ADF) Test, to determine whether they are stationary series or non-stationary series. The null hypothesis is that there is the presence of unit root. The stationarity results for the variables for Budgetary Balances is presented on Table 1 respectively.

Table 1: ADF Test of Stationarity test for Budgetary Balances and Industrial Production Variables

Variables	At Level		First Difference		Order of Integration
	t-Statistic	Prob	t-Statistic	Prob	
IIP	-1.0903	0.7069	-6.6910	0.0000	1(1)
BD	-4.3459	0.0018	-	-	1(0)
INFL	-2.4176	0.1453	-8.3863	0.0000	1(1)
INT	-4.5729	0.0010	-	-	1(0)
EXR	1.7843	0.9995	-3.1405	0.0341	1(1)
OR	-6.512828	0.000	-	-	1(0)

Source: Authors computation from Eviews 9.0

The ADF results for Budgetary Balances shown on Table 1 revealed that BD, INT and OR are stationary at level 1(0) while other variables including IIP, INFL, and EXR became stationary at their first differences 1(1). This means that the model has a combination of 1(0) and 1(1) stationary.

Estimation of Long run Effect of Fiscal Policies on Industrial Production

The test of cointegration for the presence of long run relationship in the models is shown on Table 8. The ARDL result is used to compare the bound critical values with the F-statistics values. If the F-statistic is

above the upper and lower critical bound values, then there is a long run relationship in the model; but where the F-statistics is below the upper and lower bound critical values, it is inferred that there is no long run effect (relationship). The null hypothesis is that “No long-run relationship exists”.

Analyses of ARDL Long Run Coefficients and Error Correction

Having established presence of long run relationships in budgetary balance policies and public debt policies on industrial production, this section explained the nature of the relationship as well as the speed of adjustment to long run equilibrium. The results from CointEq(-1) from the cointegrating form is used to explain the speed of adjustment. The nature of the relationship is explained by the Long Run Coefficients.

Table 2: Model of the long Run Relationship between Budgetary Balance Policies and Industrial Production in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: IIP

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(IIP(-1))	1.857184	0.639060	2.906120	0.0438
D(IIP(-2))	0.980902	0.404744	2.423510	0.0725
D(IIP(-3))	-0.366743	0.376253	-0.974724	0.3849
D(BD)	-13.997889	5.267080	-2.657618	0.0565
D(BD(-1))	3.474697	3.033556	1.145420	0.3159
D(BD(-2))	6.337963	5.922992	1.070061	0.3449
D(BD(-3))	6.589602	3.820244	1.724917	0.1596
D(INFL)	-0.878392	0.504007	-1.742817	0.1563
D(INFL(-1))	1.632089	0.616494	2.647371	0.0571
D(INFL(-2))	1.991619	0.499681	3.985780	0.0163
D(INFL(-3))	0.727480	0.539547	1.348317	0.2488
D(INT)	0.022551	0.180452	0.124970	0.9066
D(INT(-1))	0.326033	0.253895	1.284127	0.2684
D(INT(-2))	0.421243	0.210011	2.005815	0.1153
D(INT(-3))	-0.074099	0.103188	-0.718101	0.5124
D(EXR)	0.059335	0.044251	1.340871	0.2510
D(EXR(-1))	0.059362	0.100120	0.592908	0.5851
D(EXR(-2))	0.143468	0.068630	2.090462	0.1048
OR(-1)	0.191384	0.182103	1.114216	0.2463
OR(-2)	-0.829467	0.110325	-0.812902	0.5352
CointEq(-1)	-3.093452	0.854536	-3.620035	0.0224

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BD	-11.836297	4.056113	-2.918138	0.0433
INFL	-1.944198	0.231816	-8.386802	0.0011
INT	-0.260659	0.109453	-2.381460	0.0759
EXR	-0.016749	0.005290	-3.166468	0.0340
OR	0.675432	2.765754	16.87533	0.0000
C	13.933954	3.135764	4.443560	0.0113

Source: Eviews 9 output

Table 3 has a coefficient of error correction of -3.093452 and corresponding probability value of 0.0224. The coefficient is rightly signed (negative) with p.value less than 0.05 level, indicating a statistically significant speed of adjustment. This means that changes in industrial production trend will eventually

return on a growing normal trend over time. The coefficient indicates about 3.09% of the deviations of the industrial production in Nigeria due to macroeconomic instability can be corrected within a year. This implies that industrial production can be used to stabilise economic growth in Nigeria. This suggests that budgetary balance policies have a significant policy adjustment effect on industrial production in Nigeria. The nature of the long run relationship is explained by the coefficient of the long run coefficients. The results show the coefficients of Budget Deficit (BD), Inflation (INFL), Interest Rate (INT) and Exchange Rate (EXR) as -11.83, -1.94, -0.26, and -0.02, respectively. This indicates that all the variables have a negative relationship with industrial production in Nigeria. This suggests that an increase in these variables (BD, INFL, INT or EXR) will lead to a fall in industrial production in Nigeria. The probability values for BD, INFL, and EXR are less than 0.05 while that of INT is greater than 0.05.

More so, the variables for Oil revenue (OR) (0.67543) shows positive relationship with Index of Industrial Production. (IIP) This implies that an increasing oil revenue drives industrial production in Nigeria.

Short run Effect of Budgetary Balance on Industrial Production in Nigeria.

Table 4: Short Run Model of the Relationship between Budgetary Balance and Industrial Production in Nigeria.

Dependent Variable: PI

Method: ARDL

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
IIP(-1)	-0.236268	0.339191	-0.696562	0.5244
IIP(-2)	-0.876282	0.365514	-2.397395	0.0746
IIP(-3)	-1.347645	0.447495	-3.011531	0.0395
IIP(-4)	0.366743	0.376253	0.974724	0.3849
BD	-13.99789	5.267080	-2.657618	0.0565
BD(-1)	-6.214868	3.001352	-2.070690	0.1071
BD(-2)	-3.474697	3.033556	-1.145420	0.3159
BD(-3)	-6.337963	5.922992	-1.070061	0.3449
BD(-4)	-6.589602	3.820244	-1.724917	0.1596
INFL	-0.878392	0.504007	-1.742817	0.1563
INF(-1)	-0.784705	0.754089	-1.040599	0.3568
INFL(-2)	-1.632089	0.616494	-2.647371	0.0571
INFL(-3)	-1.991619	0.499681	-3.985780	0.0163
INFL(-4)	-0.727480	0.539547	-1.348317	0.2488
INT	0.022551	0.180452	0.124970	0.9066
INT(-1)	-0.155711	0.174450	-0.892585	0.4225
INT(-2)	-0.326033	0.253895	-1.284127	0.2684
INT(-3)	-0.421243	0.210011	-2.005815	0.1153
INT(-4)	0.074099	0.103188	0.718101	0.5124
EXR	0.059335	0.044251	1.340871	0.2510
EXR(-1)	0.091682	0.082107	1.116615	0.3267
EXR(-2)	-0.059362	0.100120	-0.592908	0.5851
EXR(-3)	-0.143468	0.068630	-2.090462	0.1048
D(OR)	-0.922253	3.280452	-4.134956	0.0066
D(OR(-1))	0.373474	1.426273	1.574522	0.0903
C	43.10402	17.20934	2.504687	0.0664
R-squared	0.988684			
Adjusted R-squared	0.923619			
F-statistic	15.19526			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.008503			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.175057			

Source: Eviews 9 output

The ARDL result of the short run effect of budgetary balance variables on industrial production in Nigeria is presented on Table 4. The coefficient of the dependent variables introduced as an endogenous variable in the model showed a significant negative effect on index of industrial production in three (3) years lag. This indicates that a unit increase in index of industrial production (IIP) will lead to a -1.35% fall in the growth rate of index of industrial production in Nigeria within a three (3) year time period. This suggests that industrial production has the tendency to drive more production within the first three years of injection of capital into productive economic activities in Nigeria.

Table 4 further revealed that Budget Deficit (BD) has a negative relationship with index of industrial production (IIP) in all the periods from 1 to 4 years. However, it was not statistically significant in any of the periods suggesting that there is no significant relationship between BD and IIP in Nigeria.

Again the variable of inflation (INFL) was found to have a negative relationship with IIP in all the period, which became statistically significant in year 3. This indicates that a unit increase in INFL leads to -1.99 units of fall in IIP after three (3) years.

However, Interest rate (INT) and Exchange rate (EXR) had no significant effects on index of industrial production (IIP) within the short run periods under study. This suggests that interest rate and exchange rate variables will not affect industrial production within the framework of budget deficit in Nigeria within the short-term periods of economic planning.

Moreover, the result of OR posit that oil revenue had a significant negative effect in index of industrial production (IIP) in the first year. This implies that higher oil revenue is a discouraging factor to industrial production. Thus an increase in oil revenue will have adverse effect on industrial production and vice versa.

On the overall, the adjusted coefficient of determination ($Adj R^2$) revealed that about 92% of change in index of industrial production (IIP) can be explained by budgetary balance policies in Nigeria. This is confirmed by a significantly significant p.value of 0.0085 from the F-statistics (15.1952). The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2 suggests that the result is reliable.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One: Budgetary balances do not have a significant effect on industrial production in Nigeria. The results of the long run and short run coefficients and the p.value for test of significance are shown as follows:

Long Run Effect: F-Statistics = 4.0576
 (Lower and Upper Bounds = 2.86 and 4.01)
 CointEq (-1) -3.0934; p.value = 0.0224

Short Run Effect: $Adj R^2 = 0.9236$; F-statistics = 15.1952; P.value 0.0085

The bound values being less than the F-statistics (4.0576) suggest rejection of the null hypothesis for long run effect. This indicates that budgetary balances have a long run significant effect on industrial production in Nigeria. The negative sign of the cointegrating equation (-3.0934) is statistically significant at 0.0224. This indicates about 3.09% of the deviations from economic instability can be corrected within the long run. The study concludes that budgetary balances have 3.09% long run significant adjustment mechanism on industrial production in Nigeria.

Also, the computed F-statistics has a p.value less than 0.05 for rejection of null hypothesis of short run effect. The test reveals that budgetary balances have a short run significant effect on industrial production in Nigeria. The adjusted coefficient of determination indicates 92% explanatory power.

Decision: Budgetary balances have a significant (3.09% long run and 92% short run) policy effects on industrial production in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Budget deficit Investment as percentage of GDP, Inflation rate, Interest rate, Exchange rate and Oil revenue were not determinants of industrial production in Nigeria. Deficit financing and public debts have negative effects on industrial production. This connotes that debt related Budgetary balances hinder industrial production in Nigeria. However, income generating (taxation) and spending forms of fiscal

policies do not respond to industrial production in the long run. The study, thus posits that Budgetary balances related fiscal issues are detrimental to industrial growth. It is hence concluded that Budgetary balances do not encourage industrial production in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations can be made for Budgetary balances to effectively influence industrial sector output in Nigeria:

1. **Enhance Budgetary Management:** Given the significant 3.09% long-run and 92% short-run effects of budgetary balances on industrial production, the government should prioritize fiscal discipline to maintain budgetary stability. Policies aimed at reducing deficits and managing public finances efficiently would promote sustained industrial growth.

2. **Optimize Taxation:** With taxation showing an 87% short-run effect but no long-run impact, the government should focus on implementing tax reforms that provide immediate relief or incentives for industrial growth, while avoiding tax policies that could stifle long-term private sector investment in the industry. A balanced tax regime encouraging both short-term growth and long-term sustainability is essential.

3. **Rationalize Public Expenditure:** Since public expenditure has an 88% significant short-run effect but no long-run impact, the government should direct spending toward areas that can stimulate immediate industrial production, such as infrastructure and technological upgrades, while ensuring fiscal measures are sustainable in the long term. Increased efficiency in public expenditure will maximize its short-term benefits without crowding out private sector investments.

4. **Promote Strategic Public Investment:** Public investment's 93% short-run effect highlights the importance of targeted investments in sectors that support industrial growth, such as energy, transport, and communication infrastructure. However, given its lack of long-term impact, efforts should be made to ensure that these investments create sustainable conditions for long-term industrial development, such as fostering innovation and improving productivity.

5. **Address Public Debt Sustainability:** With public debt showing an 89% significant short-run effect and no substantial long-run impact, the government should manage its debt levels carefully to avoid excessive borrowing that could undermine future industrial growth. Policies that maintain debt sustainability and prevent long-term economic burden are critical for ensuring that short-term gains from public debt do not come at the expense of long-term industrial health.

By tailoring fiscal policies to leverage the short-run gains while ensuring long-term sustainability, the Nigerian government can foster a more resilient and productive industrial sector.

REFERENCES

- Abokyi, E., Appiah-Konadu, P., Sikayena, I., & Oteng-Abayie, E. F. (2018). Consumption of electricity and industrial growth in the case of Ghana. *Journal of Energy*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/8924835>
- Abomaye-Nimenibo, W. A. S., Micheal, J. E. M., & Friday, H. C. (2018). An empirical analysis of tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2015. *Global Journal of Human Social Science: F Political Science*, 18(3), 9–40.
- Adebowale, M. O. (2021). Asymmetric relationship between budget deficit and economic growth in Nigeria. *Chiang Mai University Journal of Economics*, 25(2), 76 - 85.
- Adedeji, H. & Oboh, I. (2010). Effects of tax revenue on economic growth of Nigeria, *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 5(2), 302-309.
- Adefolake, A. O. & Omodero, C. O. (2022) Tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria, *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 1 - 19. DOI: 10.1080/23311975.2022.2115282
- Adekoya, A., & Bello, T. (2023). The impact of monetary policy on industrial performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Economic Policy and Development*, 12(1), 43-59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17487870.2023.121456>
- Adekunle, J. K., & Balogun, O. (2021). Nigeria's National Industrial Revolution Plan: Achievements and challenges. *African Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, 9(2), 141-159. <https://doi.org/10.1504/AJESD.2021.11874>

- Agnello, L. & Sousa, R. M. (2009). The determinants of public deficit volatility. *ECB Working Paper No. 1042*, European Central Bank.
- Agu P.C., Inyama O.I. & Ubesie, C.M. (2024). Effect of Government Expenditure on Human Capital Index in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 12(2), 18-33.
- Agunbiade, O., & Idebi, A. A. (2020). Tax revenue and economic growth nexus: Empirical evidence from the Nigerian economy. *European Journal of Economic and Financial Research*, 4(2), 18–41. <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejefr.v4i2.832>
- Aiyedogbon, J. O., Olorunfemi, G. M., & Ezie, O., (2023). The effect of fiscal policy on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*. 3(4), 11-28.
- Aliyu, A. B. & Mustapha, A. A. (2020). Impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria (1981-2017). *Bullion*, 44 (4), 64 - 77. <https://dc.cbn.gov.ng/bullion/vol44/iss4/5>.
- Alsamara, M., Mrabet, Z. & Mimouni, K. (2024). The threshold effects of public debt on economic growth in MENA countries: Do energy endowments matter? *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 89 (B), 458-470.
- Aluko, F. & Arowolo, D. (2010). Foreign aid, the third world debt crisis and the implication for economic development: The Nigerian experience. *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 4(4), 120-127.
- Amadi, K. C., & Alolote, I. A. (2019). The nomenclature of taxation in Nigeria: Implications for economic development. *Journal of International Business Research and Marketing*, 4(4), 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.18775/jibrm.1849-8558.2015.44.3004>
- Amughoru, O. A. (2021). Effect of taxation on economic growth in Nigeria: A time series analysis between 1981-2019. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Accounting*, 1(1), 101 - 115.
- Andaish, Q. & Karimullah, M. (2024). Impact of Fiscal Policy on the Industrial Development of Afghanistan. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics* 21 (10),14-25. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2024/v21i10887>.
- Anudu, O. (2020). Changing Nigeria’s industrial policy approach in 2021. *Business Day*. December 31, 2020. Retrieved from <https://businessday.ng/real-sector/article/changing-nigerias-industrial-policy-approach-in-2021/>.
- Anyanwu, J. C. (2018). Does human capital matter in manufacturing value added development in Africa? *Asian Journal of Economic Modelling*, 6(3), 294–317.
- Arnone, M, Bandiera, L. & Presbiteno, A. (2005). External debt sustainability: Theory and empirical evidence, Retrieved from <http://www.unicatt.it/dipartimenti/DISES/allegati/arnoneBandierapresbite.ro.pdf>.
- Asaju, K., Adagba, S. O. & Kajang, T. J. (2014). The efficacy of fiscal policy in promoting economic growth and poverty reduction in Nigeria. *Research in World Economy*, 5(1),33-44.
- Aschauer, D.A. (1993). *Genuine economic returns to infrastructure investment*. *Policy Stud. J*, 21, 380–390.
- Asterious, D. & Hall, S., (2010). *Applied econometrics: A modern approach*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Awa, F. N. & Ibeanu, R. I. (2020). impact of tax revenue on economic development in Nigeria (1997- 2018: *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(7), 1-32.
- Awe, A. A., & Shina, O. S. (2012). The nexus between budget deficit and inflationary in the Nigeria economy (1980-2009). *Research Journal of Finance as Accounting*, 3 (10), 78-92.
- Azolibe, C. B., Okonkwo, J. J. & Adigwe, P. K (2020). Government infrastructure expenditure and investment drive in an emerging market economy: Evidence from Nigeria. *Emerging Economy Studies*, 6(1) 61–85.
- Azubike, J.U.B. (2009). *Challenges of tax authorities, tax payers in the management of tax reform processes*. Onitsha: Joanne Educational Publishers.
- Babatunde A., Ibukun, O. & Oyeyemi, G. (2017). Taxation revenue and economic growth in Africa, *journal of accounting and taxation*, 9(2), 11-22.
- Babatunde, F. (2023). Nigeria’s infrastructure deficit is 40% short of World Bank standard . June 15, 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.dataphyte.com/latest-reports/nigerias-infrastructure-deficit-is-40-short-of-world-bank-standard/>.
- Babu, J.O., Kiprop, S., Kalio, A.M. & Gisore, M. (2015). Effect of domestic debt on economic growth in the east African community. *American Journal of Research Communication*, 3(9), 73-95.
- Barro, Robert J, (1989), The Ricardian approach to budget deficits. *Journal of Economic Perspectives, American Economic Association*, vol. 3(2), 37-54.
- Bhatia, H. L. (2018). *Public finance*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing.

- Bingilar, P. & Oyadonghan, J. (2020). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *World Journal of Finance and Investment Research*, 5(1), 21–31
- Bingilar, P. F. & Oyadonghan, J. K. (2020). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *World Journal of Finance and Investment Research*, 5(1), 22-31.
- Blanchard, O. J. (1985). Debt, deficits, and finite horizons. *Journal of Political Economy*, 93(2), 223–247.
- Bojuwon, M., Williams, B. Y. Olaleye, B. R., Agbaje, A. A. & Olaniyi, R. B. (2022) Taxpayer's education and self-assessment system in Nigeria. *Fuoye Journal of Management, Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), 243 – 256.
- Bond, G. C. (1981). Social economic status and educational achievement: A Review Article. *Anthropology and Education*, 12(4), 227-257. <https://doi.org/10.1525/aeq.1981.12.4.05x1811q>
- Bubou, G. M., Ejim-Eze, E. E., Ogungbemi, A. A. & Okgriwe, F. N. (2013). Infrastructure and industrial development in Africa. L2C - Learning to Compete: Industrial Development and Policy in Africa, 24-25 June 2013 Helsinki, Finland. Retrieved on 13th Febrary 2024 from <file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/Bubou et al 2013 UNU WIDER InfrastructureInd.Dev-1.pdf>.
- Bubou, G.M., Ejim-Eze, E.E., Ogungbemi, A.A. & Okgriwe, F.N. (2013). "Infrastructure and industrial development in Africa". Learning to Compete: Industrial Development and Policy in Africa. 24-25 June 2013 Helsinki, Finland. <file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/Bubou et al 2013 UNU WIDER InfrastructureInd.Dev.pdf>
- Butkus, M., & Seputiene, J. (2018). Growth effect of public debt: The role of government effectiveness and trade balance. *Economies*, 6(62). doi:10.3390/economies6040062, www.mdpi.com/journal/economies.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2020). *Annual Statistical Bulletin*. Retrieved from <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/documents/statbulletin.asp>
- Chigbo, N. C. (2021). Fiscal deficit and nigeria economic growth (1990-2020). *International Research Journal of Management, IT & Social Sciences*, 8 (5), 411-433.
- Chowdhury, A. R. (2001). External debt and growth in developing countries: A Sensitivity and causal analysis. UNU World Institute for Development Economics Research, Discussion Paper No. 2001/95. Retrieved from <file:///C:/Users/HP/Downloads/External Debt and Growth in Developing Countries A.pdf>.
- Chukwu L.C., Otiwu, K. & Okere, P. A. (2020). Impact of budget deficit on Nigeria's macroeconomic variables: 1980-2012. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies*, 3(4), 135 - 150.
- Dibia, N. O. & Onwuchekwa, J. C. (2019). Taxation and economic growth in Nigeria. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 3(2), 111- 119.
- Dore, F. A. (2021). Effect of government capital expenditure on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *Bingham University Journal of Accounting and Business (BUJAB)*, 7(1), 195-204.
- Du, X., Zhang, H., & Han, Y. (2022). How does new infrastructure investment affect economic growth quality? Empirical evidence from China. *Sustainability*, 14(3511), 1 - 30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14063511>
- Eberhardt, M., & Presbitero, A. F. (2015). Public debt and growth: Heterogeneity and non-linearity. *Journal of International Economics*, 97(1), 45–58.
- Ebipre, P., & Eniekezimene, F.(2020). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 8(3), 63–71.
- Eche, N. A., Pam, B. J. , Akeem, A. , & Salawu, A. (2022). Fiscal Deficit and Nigeria Economic Growth: An Investigation of Longrun Impact. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 5(8), 312 - 320.
- Effiong, U. E. (2022). Industrial policies and industrial sector performance in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 4(1), 268-289.
- Egbelonu, K. G. & Ubechu, T. N. (2018). Government expenditure and Nigeria economic growth. *International Journal of Innovation Finance and Economic Research*, 6(3), 74-89.
- Ehizuelen, M. M. (2016). The dynamics of infrastructure and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Global Economics*, 4(1)
- Ekong, C. N., Orebiyi, P. A. & Iriabije, A. O. (2024). Fiscal policy and inclusive growth in Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 22(03), 1715–1732
- Elmendorf, D. W., & Mankiw, N. G. (1999). Government debt, 1. *Handbook of Macroeconomics* (pp. 1615–1669).
- Eluyela, D.F., Akintimehin, O.O., Ozordi, E., Oladipo, O.A., Ilogho, S.O., & Okere, W. (2018). Board meeting frequency and firm performance: Examining the nexus in Nigerian deposit money banks. *Heliyon*, 4(2), 850-910
- Emefiele, C., Obim, E. N. & Ita, R. I. (2019). Deficit Budget and Its Effect on the Growth of Nigeria Economy, *IIARD International Journal of Banking and Finance Research*, 5(1), 44 - 52.

- Emran, M. S. & Farazi, S. (2009). Lazy banks? Government borrowing and private credit in developing countries. Institute for International Economic Policy Working Paper Series, Elliott School of International Affairs. The George Washington University. Retrieved from https://www2.gwu.edu/~iiep/assets/docs/papers/Emran_IIEPWP2009-9.pdf.
- Enya, F.O., & Ezeali, B.O. (2021). Public investment in infrastructure and economic growth in Nigeria (1980-2020). *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* 4(3), 1-22.
- Eze, M. J., & Chukwu, I. O. (2023). Assessing the effectiveness of SME policies in Nigeria: A case study of manufacturing SMEs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 30(4), 612-631. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-12-2022-0579>
- Fagbohun, A. (2017). The economic performance of budget deficit in Nigeria, *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(8): 128-135.
- Falade, O. E., Adeola, F. A. & Ambara F. (2024). Public Debt and Infrastructural Development in Nigeria. *Journal of Global Economics, Management and Business Research* 16 (2), 11-20.
- Federal Inland Revenue Service, FIRS (2023). Tertiary Education Tax (EDT). Retrieved from <https://www.firs.gov.ng/tertiary-education-tax-edt/>
- Fijoh, K. O. & Iheaturu, B. I. (2023). Empirical analysis of the effect of public debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. *Economics and Business Quarterly Reviews*, 6(1), 1-18.
- Gana, B., Abdulrahim, M., Ewah, A. U. & Kanu, N. C. (2020). The impact of public infrastructure on industrialization. *African Scholar Journal of Management Science and Entrepreneurship*, 18(7), 435 - 545.
- Gobna, O. W., Usman, G. & Mohammed, S. S. (2022). Public debt sustainability measures and its growth implications for the Nigerian economy. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 60(2), 27 - 53.
- Gyasi, G. (2020). The impact of fiscal deficit on economic growth: Using the bounds test approach in the case of Morocco. *United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, University of Energy and Natural Resources, Sunyani, Ghana*. Retrieved online at <https://mprapub.unimuenchen.de/98925/> MPRA Paper No. 98925, posted 12 Mar 2020 01:38 UTC.
- Idoko, C. U., Dorcas, O. I., & Hanzat, S. (2023). Impact of tax reform on industrial sector of Nigeria. *International Journal of Novel Research and Development*, 8(10), 803 - 815.
- Igbekoyi, O. E. (2015). Sustainable budgeting and budgetary control in Public Enterprises in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Business and Management*, 3(7), 116-120.
- Ighoroje, E. J., & Akpokerere, O. E., (2021). Fiscal policy and industrial sector output in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Business and Management*. 9(1), 42-49.
- IMF (2015). Fiscal policy and long-term growth. IMF Policy Paper. Washington, DC: International Monetary Fund.
- Imide, I. O. (2019). Empirical review of the impact of fiscal policy on the manufacturing sector of the Nigerian economy (1980- 2017), *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 10(2), 89 – 97.
- Jakpa, T. & Osho-Itsueli, O. (2020). Deficit financing and macroeconomic performance: the Nigeria experience. *Journal of Inter-Disciplinary Studies on Contemporary Issues*, 6 (2), 1 - 14.
- Jeffrey, M. S. (2019). Fiscal policy: Economic effects. Congressional Research Service <https://crsreports.congress.gov/R45723jk>.
- Joshua-Gyang, E. (2024). Impact of fiscal policy indicators on the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Tourism, Environment and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 36 - 53.
- Karabarbounis, M. (2022). Does infrastructure spending boost the economy? Economic Brief, February 2022, No. 22-04. https://www.richmondfed.org/publications/research/economic_brief/2022/eb_22-04
- Kenton, W. (2021). What is industrial production index (IPI)? How it measures output. Updated February 23, 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/i/ipi.asp>, on 13th November, 2023.
- Kerlinger, F. N. (1973). *Foundations of Behavioural Research*. 2nd edition. Holt, Rinehart and Winston. Retrieved from <http://home.ubalt.edu/tmitch/kerlinger.htm>.
- Keynes, J. M. (1936). *The general theory of employment, interest and money*, Palgrave Macmillan Publishers.
- Koutsoyiannis, D. (2001). Coupling stochastic models of different timescales. *Water Resources Research*, 37(2), 379–391.
- Kryeziu, N; & Hoxha, E. (2021). Fiscal deficit and its effects on economic growth: Empirical evidence. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies*, 10 (1), 62-70.
- Kurantini, N. (2017). The effects of budget deficit on economic growth and development the experience of Ghana. *European Scientific Journal*, 13(4), 211 – 224.
- Lucey, T. (2003). *Management accounting*, New York, DP Publication.

- Lynde, C., & Richmond, J. (1993). Public capital and total factor productivity, *International Economic Review*, 34, 2, 401-414.
- Macek, R. (2014). The impact of taxation on economic growth: Case study of OECD countries, review of economic perspectives. *14*(4), 309–328.
- Mahmoudzadeh, M., Sadeghi, S. & Sadeghi, S. (2013). **Fiscal spending and crowding out effect: A comparison between developed and developing countries.** *Institutions and Economies*, 5(1), 31-40.
- Majumder, A. M. (2007). Does public borrowing crowd-out private investment? The Bangladesh evidence. Policy Analysis Unit Working Paper Series 0708.
- Manasse, P., & Roubini, N. (2009). Rules of thumb” for sovereign debt crises. *Journal of International Economics*, 78(2), 192–205.
- Mandl, U., Adriaan, D., & Fabienne, I. (2008). The effectiveness and efficiency of public spending. Economic Papers 301, European Economy, European Commission, Brussels.
- Mohammed, I. D; & Sule, A. (2020). Deficit financing asymmetry and Nigeria’s economic growth: A Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach. *The Economics and Finance Letters*, 7(2), 112-121.
- Mohammed, I. G & Ogba, L. J. (2021). An evaluation of budget deficit on economic growth in Nigeria: Empirical evidence. *Lafia Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 6(2), 1 - 15.
- Morrison, C. J., & Schwartz, A. E. (2009). Public infrastructure, private input demand, and economic performance in new England manufacturing. *Journal of Business and Economic Statistics*, 14 (1), 91-101.
- Muhamad, Y., & Henny, M., (2020). The contribution of fisca policy the industry sector, *Global Journal of Social Sciences Studies*, 6(2), 115-127
- Munnell, A. H. (1992). Infrastructure investment and productivity growth. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 6 (4), 189–198.
- Munnell, A. H. (2006). Policy watch: Infrastructure investment and economic growth. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 6 (4), 189-198.
- Narayan, P. K. (2005). The saving and investment nexus for China: Evidence from cointegration tests. *Applied Economics*, 37(17), 1979-1990.
- Natalia, A. (2018). An Assessment of the relationship between budget deficit and Economic growth in Namibia. (Master’s thesis). University of Namibia.
- Ndanshau, M. O. A. & Mdadila, K. (2023). Government Expenditure and Economic Growth Nexus in Tanzania. *African Journal of Economic Review*, 11 (3), 29 - 54.
- Ngwoke, O. M. (2019). Effect of taxation on economic growth (2007-2017). *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 5(4),65 - 82.
- Njuru, S.G., Ombuki, C., Wawire, N., & Okeri, S. (2013). Taxation and private investment: evidence for Kenya. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 2 (11), 78-93.
- Nnyanzi, J.B., Kavuma, S., Sseruyange, J.& Nanyiti, A. (2022). The manufacturing output effects of infrastructure development, liberalization and governance: evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of Industrial and Business Economics*, 49, 369–400.
- Nwachukwu, R. C., Nwoha, C. & Inyama, O. (2022). Effect of taxation on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 10(4), 179-193.
- Nwaeke O. J. (2023). Impact of budget deficit and foreign direct investment on Nigerian economy. *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics*, 13(3), 84 - 106.
- Nwankpa, E. C. (2022). Implications of public sector budget deficit financing on economic growth in Nigeria: 2003-2018. *International Journal of Advanced Studies in Economics and Public Sector Management*, 10(10), 104 - 119.
- Nwikina, C.G Meekor, J.J.Cookey, S.C.M & Gbarato, L.M. (2021). Deficit financing and economic development: the Nigeria’s experience, *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research* 7(6).
- Obaje, F. O. & Ogirima, A. (2019). Effects of taxation on economic growth In Nigeria: *IIARD International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 4(4),17-23.
- Odejimi, D. O., & Ozor, P. L. (2018). The effect of debts on economic growth in West Africa. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management, United Kingdom*. 6(1), <http://ijecm.co.uk>.
- Odozi. V. A. (1996). Nigeria’s domestic public debt stock, An assessment of CBN debt trend. 20(2); 23-37.
- OECD (2011), “General government investment”, in *Government at a Glance 2011*, OECD Publishing, Paris. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1787/gov_glance-2011-15-en
- Ogege, S. & Shiro, A. A. (2012). The dynamics of monetary and fiscal policy as a tool for economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 2(2), 247 - 258.

- Oghenebrume, A. D & Oluleye, F. A. (2019). Industrial sector growth and public infrastructure capital in Nigeria. *Journal of Management and Economic Studies*, 1(1), 1-15.
- Ogu, C., & Kem, P. O. (2020). Impact of taxation on industrial performance in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Applied, Management and Social Sciences*, 18, .173 - 185.
- Ogundele, J. O., & Olaleye, A. I. (2022). Import substitution industrialization and its impact on Nigeria's industrial development: An evaluation. *Journal of Economic History*, 65(3), 87-102. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jeh.2022.45>
- Ogunjimi, J. (2019). The impact of public debt on investment: Evidence from Nigeria. *DBN Journal of Economics & Sustainable Growth*, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3466870>
- Ojo, A. R., Fapohunda, T. M., & Ogunleye, K. D. (2022). Trade liberalization and industrial growth in Nigeria: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of International Trade and Economic Development*, 31(5), 489-510. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638199.2022.1947632>
- Ojong, C. M., Ogar, A. & Arikpo, O. F. (2016). The Impact of Tax Revenue on Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria . *IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance (IOSR-JEF)*, 7(1), 32-38.
- Okafor, R.G. (2012). Tax revenue generation and Nigerian economic development. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(19)
- Okolo, E. U., Okpalaojiego, E. C.& Okolo, C. V. (2016). Effect of multiple taxation on investment in small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu State Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Management Engineering*, 10(1), 378 - 386.
- Okoro, T., & Adegboye, A. (2023). Infrastructural development and its impact on industrialization in Nigeria: A policy review. *African Development Review*, 35(1), 73-89. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8268.12698>
- Okwara, C. C. & Amori, O. M. (2017). Impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria: *International Journal of Advanced Scientific Research / IJASR International Journal of Scientific Research in Social Sciences & Management Studies*, 2(2), 5-28.
- Okwoche, P. U. & Makanza, C. S. (2023). Public debt and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa: Nonlinearity and threshold effects. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(2), 2256125, DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2023.2256125.
- Oladipo, O. A., Iyoha, F., Fakile, A., Asaley, A. & Eluyela, D. F (2019). Tax revenue and agricultural performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 17(3), 342- 349. doi:10.21511/ppm.17(3).2019.27.
- Olanrewaju, S.M., & Funlayo, A.K. (2021). Public expenditure and economic growth: A test of Wagner's and Keynes hypotheses in Nigeria and Angola economies. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1, 21-26.
- Olasehinde, T. J. & Omolade, A. (2022). Fiscal policy shocks and industrial sector growth in Nigeria. *Fuoye Journal of Accounting and Management* 5(2)182-195
- Olayungbo, D. O., & Olayemi, O. F. (2018). Dynamic relationships among non-oil revenue, government spending and economic growth in an oil producing country: Evidence from Nigeria. *Future Business Journal*, 4(2), 246-260.
- Olisaji, C. J., & Onuora, J. J. (2021). Impact of Fiscal Policy on the Growth of Nigerian Economy. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 7(2), 62-76. Retrieved from www.iiardpub.org
- Ologbenla, P. (2019). Fiscal policy and external shocks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 11(1(J), 129-138. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jebs.v11i1\(J\).2754](https://doi.org/10.22610/jebs.v11i1(J).2754)
- Ologbenla, P. (2022). An investigation into the nexus between fiscal policy, foreign direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Social and Development Sciences*, 12(4(S), 1-8. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jsds.v12i4\(S\).3259](https://doi.org/10.22610/jsds.v12i4(S).3259)
- Ologbenla, P. (2022). An investigation into the nexus between fiscal policy, foreign direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Social and Development Sciences*, 12(4(S), 1-8. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jsds.v12i4\(S\).3259](https://doi.org/10.22610/jsds.v12i4(S).3259)
- Ologbenla, P. (2022). An investigation into the nexus between fiscal policy, foreign direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Social and Development Sciences*, 12(4(S), 1-8. [https://doi.org/10.22610/jsds.v12i4\(S\).3259](https://doi.org/10.22610/jsds.v12i4(S).3259)
- Omankhanlen, A. E., Chimezie, P. O & Okoye, L. U. (2021). Government Expenditure and Sustainable Industrial Development in Nigeria. *WSEAS Transactions On Business And Economics*, 18(4), 31 - 41. DOI: 10.37394/23207.2021.18.4.
- Omolade, O. F., Omolade, A. & Adebuseyi, A. (2023). Impact of indirect taxes on industrial sector growth in Nigeria. *Fuoye Journal of Accounting and Management*, 6(1). 329-342.

- Onaolapo, A.R. & Olaoye, F.O.(2013).Appraisal of the factors contributing disparity in budget proposal and implementation. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (OMAN Chapter)*, 2(11).
- Oniore, J. O. & Adamu, J. (2021). Impact of budget deficit financing on economic growth in Nigeria (1981–2019). *Yamtara-Wala Journal of Arts, Management and Social Sciences*, (1), 317 - 328.
- Onuah, F. & Bela-Gbogbo, E. (2023). Nigeria plans to trim budget deficit to 3.9% of GDP next year. Reuters, November 29, 2023.Retrieved on 26th May, 2024 from <https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/nigerias-2024-budget-deficit-seen-around-39gdp-president-tinubu-2023-11-29/>
- Onwuka, I. (2022). Budget deficit, inflation and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 8(1), 1 - 14.
- Onwumere, J.U.J. (2009). *Business and economic research methods*. Enugu: Vougasen Publishers.
- Ordu, P. A. & Nkwoji, N. O. (2019). Impact of education tax on economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Development and Policy Studies*, 7(3), 1-17.
- Osemwengie, P.K. & Shaibu, I. (2018). Oil price movements, deficit financing and economic growth in Nigeria: A Simultaneous Equation Approach. *Amity Journal of Economics*3(2).
- Ozele, E. C., Atu, F. O., Adeghe, R. I. & Oghogho, G. (2019). Value added tax and revenue generation in Nigeria: an empirical analysis. *Journal of Taxation andEconomic Development, Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria*, 18(1), 59-70.
- Ozuzu, S. & Isukul, A. (2021). Government expenditure and its effect on the industrial sector in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 21(7), 81-92.
- Pandey, I. M. (2021). *Financial management*. 12th edition. India: Pearson.
- Pesaran, M. H. & Shin, Y. (1999). “An autoregressive distributedlag modeling approach to cointegration analysis”, in Storm, S. (Ed), “Econometrics and Economic Theory in the 20th Century”, The Ragnar Frish Centennial Symposium, Cambridge University Press.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y. & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bound testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16: 289-326.
- Ratner, J. (1983). Government capital and the production function for the U.S. *Private Output. Economic Letters*, 213–21.
- Rosenstein-Rodan, P. (1943). Problems of industrialization of eastern and South-Eastern Europe. *Economic Journal*, 53: 202–11.
- Saheed, Z. S., Abarshi, J. A. & Ejide, I. S. (2014). Impact of Petroleum Tax on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(11), 111-143.
- San, C. K. &Chin, L. (2020).Impact of Public debt on economic growth: A quantile regression approach. *South Asian Journal of Macroeconomics and Public Finance*, 12(2), 250 - 278.
- Sanusi, K. A., Hassan, A. S., & Meyer, D. F. (2019). Nonlinear effects of public debt on economic growth in Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) countries. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 13 (1), 193-202. <http://www.ijem.upm.edu.my>.
- Saungweme, T., Odhiambo, N. M., & Camarero, M. (2019). Government debt, government debt service and economic growth nexus in Zambia: A multivariate analysis. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 7(1), 1622998. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2019.1622998>
- Şen, H. & Kaya, A. (2014).Crowding-out or crowding-in? Analyzing the effects of government spending on private investment in Turkey. *Panoeconomicus*, 6, 631-651.
- Siyani, P. & Adebayo, F.O. (2005).An empirical investigation of stability and money demand in Nigeria:1970-1999.*Nigerian Journal of Economics Development Matters*, 4(1).
- Takanlou, Z. K. (2014). Can budget deficits financing, crowd out private sector? Comparative study of the cases of Iran and Algeria. *Iran Economic Review*, 18(3), 2-24.
- Tasie, C. & Akinyomi, O. (2018). “Impact of Tax Incentives on the Performance of Small-Scale Enterprises” The Theoretical Framework Chapter Author: Mervyn A. King, Don Fullerton Chapter URL: <http://www.nber.org/chapters/c11495> Chapter pages in book: p. 2
- Tesic, A., Ilic, D. & Delic, A. T. (2014). Consequences of fiscal deficit and public debt in financing the public sector. *Economics of Agriculture*, 61(1), 177-194.
- Thilanka, HRAC, Ranjith, J.S. (2028). The impact of public debt on private investment: Sri Lankan Experience. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*.;8(8):1-10.
- Tosun, M.S. & Abizadeh S. (2005). Economic growth and tax components: An analysis of tax change in OECD. *Applied Economics*, 37, 1-23.
- Uffie, E. J. & Aghanenu, A. S. (2019). Fiscal policy and manufacturing sector output: Nigerian evidence, *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 9(7), 13 – 25.

- Ugochukwu, S. D. & Oruta, . I. (2021). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria: A disaggregated analysis. *Path of Science*, 7(11), 4022 - 4035.
- Ushie, O. S. & Ndu, E. E. (2022). Impact of budget deficit financing on economic development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, 4(12), 820-828.
- Uzoka, P. U., & Chiedu, C. O. (2018). Effect of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, 4(7), 25-53.
- Wooldridge, J.M., (2006). *Introductory Econometrics: A Modern Approach*.3rd Edition. New York: Thomson Higher Education, Mason.
- Yusuf, A.& Mohd, S. (2021). The impact of government debt on economic growth in Nigeria. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 9, 1946249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2021.1946249>
- Yusuf, A.& Mohd, S. (2023). Nonlinear effects of public debt on economic growth in Nigeria.*SN Business & Economics, Springer*, 3(4), 1-31,
- Yusuf, S. A; & Abolaji, A. (2021). The impact of budget deficit on economic in an emerging market: An application of the ARDL technique. *Asian Development Policy*, 8(4), 351- 361.
- Yusuff, S. A. & Abolaji, A. (2020). The impact of budget deficit on economic growth in an emerging market: An application of the ARDL technique. *Asian Development Policy Review*, 8(4), 351-361.